

Hammett equation :

A linear free-energy correlation was attempted by casting the data into an extended form of Hammett equation⁴.

$$\log k/k_0 = \rho \sum_1 \sigma_1$$

The σ_0 value for methoxy and σ_m values of the various substituents ($-\text{NO}_2$, $-\text{CO}_2\text{H}$, $-\text{Br}$, $-\text{Cl}$) were taken from literature⁵ to calculate $\sum_1 \sigma_1$. From the slope of the Hammett plot of $\log k_2$ vs $\sum_1 \sigma_1$, ρ was found to be -7.63 .

Fig. 1. Hammett plot for NBSA bromination of *p*-substituted anisoles.

For NBS bromination of the above anisoles the ρ value was found⁶ to be -7.85 . The magnitude of ρ and its negative sign suggest that the above NBS and NBSA brominations proceed through a carbocationic intermediate.

To compare the relative reactivities of Br_2 , NBS and NBSA we have investigated the bromination of PNA by these reagents in 50% aq. HOAc at 303 K. NBS is only slightly more reactive than Br_2 but NBSA is 18 times more reactive than Br_2 (Table 1).

TABLE 1—RELATIVE REACTIVITIES OF BROMINATING AGENTS

Brominating Agent	$k_1 \times 10^6$ (sec ⁻¹)	Relative reactivity
Br_2	1.05	1.0
NBS	1.77	1.7
NBSA	19.1	18.2

[PNA] = 0.020 M; 50% aq. HOAc, 303 K;
[Br_2] = [NBS] = [NBSA] = 0.002 M.

Also, NBSA is a crystalline solid which is easier to handle than liquid Br_2 . Thus, there is a great potential for the use of NBSA as a brominating agent for aromatic compounds.

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Kinetics and Mechanism of Ce(IV) Oxidation of 4-Methyl Morpholine in Perchloric Acid Media

BHARAT SINGH

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002

and

G. K. SETH*

Department of Chemistry, V. S. S. D. College, Kanpur

Manuscript received 1 June 1982, revised 1 March 1983, accepted 1 July 1983

RECENTLY, ceric perchlorate oxidation of some substrates in perchloric acid media has been reported¹⁻¹¹. In some cases the mechanistic approach has been based via free radical formation. Thus, mechanism suggested by various authors is not uniform and any inference made on analogy would be naive. The present study aims at getting more definite information regarding the mechanism of oxidation of 4-methyl morpholine by Ce(IV) in perchloric acid solutions.

Experimental

The sample of 4-methyl morpholine was E. Merck product. All other chemicals were of B.D.H., A.R. grade. The rate of oxidation was determined titrimetrically⁹.

Results and Discussion

The results obtained under different conditions are listed in Table 1. The constant value of pseudo first order rate constant shows that the reaction follows first order kinetics with respect to ceric

* Author for correspondence.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING [REACTANTS] ON REACTION RATE

Temp. °C	[Ce(IV)]* × 10 ³ M	[M]** × 10 ³ M	[H ⁺]*** M	(μ) M	10 ⁴ k ₁ sec ⁻¹	k ₂ × 10 ³ = k ₁ /[M] or [H ⁺] l mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
35	1.00	10.00	1.50	2.02	3.52	—
35	1.25	10.00	1.50	2.02	3.01	—
35	1.42	10.00	1.50	2.02	2.65	—
35	1.66	10.00	1.50	2.02	2.48	—
35	2.00	10.00	1.50	2.02	2.23	—
35	2.50	10.00	1.50	2.02	1.96	—
35	4.00	10.00	1.50	2.02	1.11	—
35	2.00	3.34	1.50	2.02	0.70	2.09
35	2.00	4.00	1.50	2.02	0.91	2.27
35	2.00	5.00	1.50	2.02	1.18	2.36
35	2.00	6.60	1.60	2.02	1.47	2.22
35	2.00	8.00	1.50	2.02	1.64	2.05
35	2.00	13.32	1.50	2.02	2.95	2.21
35	2.00	10.00	0.62	2.02	0.88	0.14
35	2.00	10.00	0.80	2.02	1.13	0.14
35	2.00	10.00	1.36	2.02	1.97	0.15
35	2.00	10.00	1.50	2.02	2.20	0.15
35	2.00	10.00	1.75	2.02	2.45	0.14
35	2.00	10.00	2.00	2.02	2.90	0.15
35	2.00	10.00	1.50	2.52	2.48	—
35	2.00	10.00	1.50	3.02	2.91	—
35	2.00	10.00	1.50	3.32	3.14	—
35	2.00	10.00	1.50	3.82	3.43	—
35	2.00	10.00	1.50	4.12	3.71	—
30	4.00	10.00	1.50	2.02	0.75	—
35	4.00	10.00	1.50	2.02	1.11	—
40	4.00	10.00	1.50	2.02	1.49	—
45	4.00	10.00	1.50	2.02	2.61	—

* [Ce(IV)] = [Ceric perchlorate]
 ** [M] = [4-Methyl morpholine]
 *** [H⁺] = [Perchloric acid]

perchlorate. Pseudo first order rate constants obtained at different concentrations of both 4-methyl morpholine and hydrogen ion were directly proportional to the concentrations of 4-methyl morpholine and hydrogen ions, respectively, indicating thereby first order dependence of the reaction on each 4-methyl morpholine and H⁺ ions. This is also confirmed by constant values of k₂ i.e. k₁/[H⁺] or [4-methyl morpholine] given in the last column of Table 1. The work has been carried out at four temperatures. The energy of activation was found to be 13.8 k cal mole⁻¹. The effect of ionic strength of the medium (varied by adding suitable amounts of sodium perchlorate) was also studied and the results are given in the table. The equivalents of Ce(IV) required per mole of 4-methyl morpholine were found to be eighteen. Formic acid was identified as an end product by chromatography.

The increase in velocity with increasing acidity may be explained generally in terms of a model which portrays the Ce(IV) coordinated by both N and O ligands. The quality of Ce(IV) as an electron sink is not fully sensed by O ligand as long as the electron pair of the N ligand occupies one of the positions available around the metal ion. H⁺ competes with Ce(IV) as an electron pair acceptor with increasing acidity and Ce(IV) character as an electron sink is enhanced when N is protonated and

electron transfer from the coordinated O ligand takes place.

The rate vs acidity reaction profiles obtained here may be explained in terms of reaction routes involving certain active species whose concentrations are controlled by the acidity of the medium. The main species¹²⁻¹⁶ in HClO₄ are [Ce(H₂O)₉]⁴⁺ and hydrolysed species [Ce(OH)(H₂O)₇]³⁺ and [Ce(OH)₂(H₂O)₆]²⁺.

The evidence¹⁶ for dimeric species (Ce-O-Ce)⁶⁺, (HO-Ce-O-CeOH)⁴⁺ etc. has been given. Their importance can be ignored as the predominant species is monomeric¹⁷ in perchloric acid concentration range 0.2-2.0 M. The concentration of various species of Ce(IV) existing in HClO₄ are governed by the following equilibria.

The latest values of K₁ and K₂ are 6.4 and 0.12, respectively¹⁸. The fraction of Ce(IV) which exists as unhydrolysed species may be calculated by the following equation,

$$\frac{1}{\text{Ce}^{4+}} = 1 + \frac{K_1}{[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{K_1 K_2}{[\text{H}^+]^2} \quad \dots (3)$$

where ^aCe⁴⁺ refers to the unhydrolysed Ce⁴⁺ species. Calculations⁹ according to equation (3) show that ^aCe⁴⁺ increases with acidity in HClO₄ solutions (Table 2). This unhydrolysed species is probably the most active species of Ce(IV) in the experimental conditions of the reaction medium and an increase in the acid concentration would lead to an increase in the observed rate.

TABLE 2—CONCENTRATION DISTRIBUTION OF Ce(IV) SPECIES AT DIFFERENT ACIDITIES

[H ⁺] M	^a Ce ⁴⁺	^a Ce(OH) ₂ ²⁺	^a Ce(OH) ³⁺
0.6	0.072	0.155	0.773
1.0	0.122	0.096	0.782
2.0	0.227	0.053	0.720
3.0	0.310	0.029	0.661
4.0	0.377	0.023	0.600
5.0	0.432	0.020	0.548

In acid solutions 4-methyl morpholine (M) will be protonated as given below

Considering the steps (i)-(iii) and applying steady state conditions with respect to M^+ the rate law may be written as eqn. (4) with safe assumption that the values of k_2 is low so that $k_{-1}^1 \gg k_2$ [Ce(IV)] holds good.

$$-\frac{d[Ce(IV)]}{dt} = \frac{k_1^1 k_2}{k_{-1}^1} [Ce(IV)][M][H^+] \quad \dots \text{(4)}$$

$$\text{or rate} = k_1^1 [Ce(IV)][M][H^+] \quad \dots \text{(5)}$$

$$\text{where } k_1^1 = k_1^1 k_2 / k_{-1}^1$$

At constant $[H^+]$, eqn. (5) may be written as eqn. (6),

$$\text{rate} = k_2^1 [Ce(IV)][M] \quad \dots \text{(6)}$$

At constant $[M]$, eqn. (6) may be written as eqn. (7)

$$\text{rate} = k_1 [Ce(IV)] \quad \dots \text{(7)}$$

The rate laws (5), (6) and (7) are in complete agreement with observed kinetics. Interaction between two similarly charged species in the proposed rate determining step (ii) is in complete accord with positive effect of ionic strength of the medium leading to rate law (5) as valid.

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Reaction of β -Mercaptoethanol with α , β -Unsaturated Steroidal Ketones : Synthesis of Steroidal Thioethers

SHAFIULLAH*, SHAMSUZZAMAN and B. Z. KHAN
Steroidal Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry,
Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 001

Manuscript received 20 May 1983, revised 6 June 1983,
accepted 15 September 1983

IN continuation to our previous studies¹⁻⁴, we carried out the synthesis of steroidal thioethers (III-VII) by the reaction of β -mercaptoethanol with α , β -unsaturated 7-ketosteroids (I and II) in acetic acid using BF_3 -etherate as catalyst. By this method we got some new thioethers (III, VI, VII) in addition to IV and V, which were obtained (after acetylation of the products) by the previous method⁴. Thioethers had been tested for antiinflammatory, neurotropic, bactericidal, fungicidal, anticholesteremic and hypolipemic activities⁵⁻⁸. Few others were reported as tranquilizers⁹. Steroidal thioethers were also used to assay steroidal hormones using radio-immunoassay technique¹⁰. These physiological observations inspired us to undertake the present work.

Characterization of these thioethers was made on the basis of their spectral data.

3β -Acetoxycholest-5-en-7-one (I)¹¹ on treatment with β -mercaptoethanol in acetic acid, using BF_3 -etherate as catalyst afforded five thioethers.

3β -Acetoxy-4 α -acetoxyethylmercaptocholest-5-en-7-one (III), m.p. 69-70°, yield 32%. IR $\nu_{\max}$:

O
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1740, 1025 (O-C-CH₂), 1665 cm⁻¹ (C=C-C=O).
NMR : δ 5.68 (s, 1H, C6-H), 4.2 (m, 3H, -OCH₂, C3 α -H), 2.86 (m, 3H, -SCH₂, C4 β -H), 2.02 (s, 6H, 2X-O-C-CH₃). (Found : C, 70.74 ; H, 9.31. C₃₃H₅₂O₅S requires C, 70.71 ; H, 9.29%).

3β -Acetoxyethylmercaptocholest-5-en-7-one (IV), m.p. 88-89°, yield 23%. IR $\nu_{\max}$: 1735, 1020

O
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(O-C-CH₂), 1660 cm⁻¹ (C=C-C=O). NMR :
 δ 5.6 (s, 1H, C6-H), 4.18 (t, 2H, -OCH₂), 2.65 (m, 3H, -SCH₂, C3 α -H), 2.02 (s, 3H, O-C-CH₃). (Found : C, 74.14 ; H, 9.99. C₃₁H₅₀O₅S requires C, 74.10 ; H, 9.96%).